

CEDE PROJECT SURVEY

* Obligatoria

1. Which is your collective?

- Academic responsible
- Teaching staff
- Company
- Enginnering associations
- Student representatives
- Others

2. Do you consider that the modules need some additional theoretical question?. If yes, please add the information about the additional questions. *

3. Do you consider that is it necessary to include some additional activity in the modules?. If not, please add your comments. *

4. Do you find appropriate the evaluation tools? If not, please suggest some additional ones. *

5. Do you consider that schedule is appropriate?. If not, please add your comments. *

6. Do you consider that webpage is useful?. Please add the drawbacks that you consider. *

7. Do you believe that is necessary to add some additional competences?. Please indicate it. *

8. Do you believe that will be possible to include the modules in the academic program?. If not, please indicate why. *

Este contenido no está creado ni respaldado por Microsoft. Los datos que envíe se enviarán al propietario del formulario.